

FORMULATION AND INVITRO EVALUATION OF DOXORUBICIN SUSTAINED RELEASE AND PALANOSETRON IMMEDIATE RELEASE LAYER IN BILAYER TABLET

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ABSTRACT

Doxorubicin is a chemotherapeutic drug which can cause severe nausea during treatment to relieve the patient from nausea and vomiting effects we selected palonosetron drug. So we prepared and evaluated Bilayered tablets containing Doxorubicin SR and palonosetron IR layered tablets by wet granulation method. A new analytical method has been developed to estimate the doxorubicin and palonosetron and validated for the use in this study. The prepared formulations evaluated for physiochemical properties and found to be within limits. The optimized formulation F6 (palonosetron IR) contains the average thickness of 2.52 ± 0.54 average hardness of 4.3 ± 0.21 , average weight of 151 ± 0.06 , friability of 0.41% and disintegration time 2min 30sec. The prepared dry mixer for the sustained release maintained the physiochemical properties of tablets such as thickness, hardness, weight variation, friability. The optimized formulation F5 (doxorubicin SR) contains the average thickness of 3.44 ± 0.21 average hardness of 7.1 ± 0.55 , friability of 0.31%. The F5 formulation which releases the doxorubicin in sustained manner in up to 12 hours and Palonosetron immediate release F6 formulation showed 98% drug release with in 60min. both optimised formulations are compressed together to prepare bilayer tablets and dissolution data of bilayer tablet proved there is no change in drug release profile, and FTIR studies proved no interaction between polymers and drug hence successful in developing bilayer tablet of doxorubicin and palonosetron.

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INTRODUCTION

Chemotherapy is a long and painful experience for cancer patients. During this period of time the patient will be subjected to number of chemical compounds which causes mild to severe side effects. One drug that is used in cancer treatment is doxorubicin Just as the other drugs doxorubicin causes mild to severe nausea and vomiting. To reduce this effect palonosetron is generally employed. In this study we successfully prepared a combined dosage form to reduce the side effects of doxorubicin as well as to reduce the number of tablet intake to improve the patient compliance. To deliver this formulation bilayer tablet as dosage form selected.

Despite phenomenal advances in the inhalable, injectable, transdermal, nasal and other routes of administration, the unavoidable truth is that oral drug delivery remains well ahead of the pack as the preferred delivery route. There are of course many applications and large markets for non-oral products and the technologies that deliver them. However, if it is a viable option, oral drug delivery will be chosen in all but the most exceptional circumstances. Moreover, if the oral route is not immediately viable, pharmaceutical companies will often invest resources in making it viable, rather than plumping for an alternative delivery method^{1,4}.

Over the last 3 decades, many novel oral therapeutic systems have been invented along with the appreciable development of drug delivery technology. Although these advanced DDS are manufactured or fabricated in traditional pharmaceutical formulations, such as tablets, capsules, sachets, suspensions, emulsions and solutions they are superior to the conventional oral dosage forms in terms of their therapeutic efficacies, toxicities and stabilities.^{1,2,5}

Novel dual release tablets

Synonyms: Bilayer tablets, multi-layer matrix tablets, bilayer caplets.

Definition:

Dual release tablet is a unit compressed tablet dosage form intended for oral administration. It contains two parts in which one part having conventional or immediate release part another one is sustained or controlled release part.

Bi layer tablets: Several pharmaceutical companies are currently developing bilayer tablets, for a variety of reasons like patent extension, therapeutic marketing to name a few

Applications^{3,4}

Used in the combination therapy.

- Used to deliver the loading dose and sustained dose of the same or different drugs.
- Used in the combination therapy.
- Used for bilayer floating tablet in which one layer is floating layer another one is release layer of the drug.
- Used to deliver the two different drugs having different release profiles.

Advantages

- Extension of a conventional technology.
 - Potential use of single entity feed granules.
- Separation of incompatible components
- Patient compliance is enhanced leading to improve drug regimen efficacy.
 - Patient convenience is improved because fewer daily doses are required. compared to traditional delivery system.
 - Maintain physical and chemical stability.
 - Retain potency and ensure dose accuracy.

Disadvantages^{3,4,7}

- Adds complexity and bilayer rotatory presses are expensive.
- Insufficient hardness, Layer separation, reduced yield.
- Inaccurate individual layer weight control.
- Cross contamination between the layers.

Ideal properties for bilayer tablets press

- Preventing capping and separation of the two individual layers that constitute the bilayer tablet.
- Preventing cross-contamination between the two layers.
- Producing a clear visual separation between the two layers.
- High yield and accurate and individual weight control of the two layers.

Types of bilayer tablet press¹⁴

1. Single sided tablet press.
2. Double sided tablet press.
3. Bilayer tablet press with displacement monitoring.

Single sides press^{6,8,14,16}

- The simplest design is a single sided press with both chambers of the doublet feeder separated from each other. Each chamber is gravity or forced fed with different power, thus producing the two individual layers of the tablets.
- When the die passes under the feeder, it is at first loaded with the first layer powder followed by the second layer powder.
- Then the entire tablet is compressed in one or two steps.

Limitations of single sided press

- No weight monitoring / control of the individual layers.
- No distinct visual separation between the two layers.
- Very short first layer dwell time due to the small compression roller, possibly resulting in poor de-aeration, capping, and hardness problems.
- This may be corrected by reducing the turret-rotation speed (to extend the well time) but with the consequence of lower tablet output.

Multi-layer compression basics^{9,10,11,12}

Presses can be designed specifically for multi-layer compression or a standard double-sided press can be converted for multi-layers:

The multilayer tablets concept has been long utilized to develop sustained release formulation; such a tablet has a fast releasing layer and may contain bilayer or triple layers to sustain the drug release.

The pharmacokinetic advantage relies on the fact that drug release from fast releasing granules leads to a sudden rise in blood concentration however, the blood level is maintained at steady state as the drug is released from the sustained granules.

Dwell time

Dwell time is defined as the time during which compression force is above 90% of its peak value longer dwell times are a major factor in producing a quality tablet, especially when compressing a complex formulation.

Compression force

Many bilayer formulations requires a first layer compression force of less than 100 daN in order to retain the ability to bond with the second layer. Above 100daN, this ability may be lost, bonding between both layers must not be sufficient, resulting in low hardness of the bilayer tablet and separation of the two layers.

Double sided tablet presses

- 1) In most double sided tablet presses with automated production control use compression force to monitor and control tablet weight.
- 2) The effective peak compression force exerted on each individual tablet or layer is measured by the control system at main compression of the layer
- 3) This measured peak compression force is the signal used by the control system to reject out of tolerance tablets and correct the die fill depth when required.

Bilayer tablet press with displacement¹⁵

The displacement tablet weight control principle is fundamentally different from the principle based upon compression force.

When measuring displacement, the control system sensitivity does not depend on the tablet weight but depends on the applied pre-compression force.

Advantages

- Weight monitoring / control for accurate and independent weight control of the individual layers.
- Low compression force exerted on the first layer to avoid capping and separation of the two individual layers.
- Independence from the machine stiffness
- Increased dwell time at pre-compression of both first and second layer to provide sufficient hardness at maximum turret speed.
- Maximum prevention of cross-contamination between the two layers
- Clear visual separation between the two layers and maximized yield.

Controlled / sustained release drug delivery system^{1,2,10,12,18,19}

For many disease states the ideal dosage regimen is that by which an acceptable therapeutic concentration of drug at the site (s) of action is attained immediately and is then maintained constant for the desired duration of the treatment.

Over the past 30 years as the expense and complication involved in marketing new drug entities have increased, with concomitant recognition of the therapeutic advantage of modified release per oral dosage forms, greater attention has been focused on development of sustained, controlled release and delayed release system.

There are several reasons for the attractiveness of this dosage form. It is generally recognized that for many disease states, a substantial number of therapeutically effective compounds already exist. The effectiveness of these drugs however is often limited by side effects or the necessity to administer the compound in a clinical setting.

Immediate release drug delivery system^{1,4,6,9,15,22}

The scenario of pharmaceutical drug delivery are expeditiously challenging, but conventional pharmaceutical dosage forms are still dominating. Immediate release dosage forms are those wherein $\geq 85\%$ of labeled amount dissolves within 30 min. Superdisintegrants are used to improve the efficacy of solid dosage forms. The basic approach used in the formulation of the tablet is the use of superdisintegrants like croscarmellose, sodium starch glycolate, and Crospovidone, etc. These superdisintegrants provide instantaneous disintegration of the tablet after administration in the stomach. Thus, decreasing the disintegration time which in turn enhances drug dissolution rate. The rapid disintegration may be due to the rapid uptake of water from the medium, swelling, burst effect and thereby promoting bioavailability. Tablets formulations are mostly preferred because of the low cost of manufacture, package, shipment, increased stability. Among various dosage forms used for oral drug delivery, tablets are one of the most successful and marketable drug delivery regimens as it provides several advantages over another form of dosage forms.

The objective study is to prepare and evaluate Bilayered tablets containing Doxorubicin SR and palonosetron IR layered tablets by wet granulation method.

Materials used:

Doxorubicin and palonosetron [API] Bought from Natco pharma pvt ltd., HPMC, PVP K30, xanthum gum, Magnesium Stearate, Crospovidone, Cross carmellose sodium, Sodium starch glycolate, Micro Crystalline Cellulose are Bought from SD Fine-Chem. Pvt., Mumbai, India.

PREFORMULATION STUDIES:^{14, 18, 25, 26, 27}

The goals of the preformulation study are:

- ❖ To establish the necessary physicochemical characteristics of a new drug substance.
- ❖ To determine its kinetic release rate profile.
- ❖ To establish its compatibility with different excipients.

Hence, preformulation studies on the obtained sample of drug include colour, taste, solubility analysis, melting point determination and compatibility studies and flow properties.

METHOD DEVELOPMENT:

Method development for simultaneous estimation of doxorubicin and palonosetron in prepared Pharmaceutical dosage forms includes the following steps:

1. Selection of detection wavelength (λ_{\max})
2. Selection of column
3. Selection of mobile phase
4. Selection of flow rate
5. Preparations and procedures

Preparations and procedures:**Preparation of Phosphate buffer :(PH 4.6)**

Weighed 6.8 grams of KH_2PO_4 was taken into a 1000ml beaker, dissolved and diluted to 1000ml with HPLC water, adjusted the pH to 4.6 with ortho phosphoric acid.

Preparation of mobile phase:

A mixture of pH 4.6 Phosphate buffer 300 mL (30%), 700 mL of Acetonitrile (70%) are taken and degassed in ultrasonic water bath for 5 minutes. Then this solution is filtered through 0.45 μ filter under vacuum filtration.

Diluent Preparation:

Mobile phase is used as Diluent.

Preparation of the individual Doxorubicin standard preparation:

10mg of Doxorubicin working standard was accurately weighed and transferred into a 10ml clean dry volumetric flask and about 2ml of mobile phase is added. Then it is sonicated to dissolve it completely and made volume upto the mark with the diluent. (Stock solution). Further 10.0 ml from the above stock solution is pipette into a 100 ml volumetric flask and was diluted upto the mark with diluent.

Preparation of the individual Palonosetron standard preparation:

10mg of Palonosetron working standard was accurately weighed and transferred into a 10ml clean dry volumetric flask and about 2ml of mobile phase is added. Then it is sonicated to dissolve it completely and made volume upto the mark with the diluent. (Stock solution). Further 10.0 ml from the above stock solution is pipette into a 100 ml volumetric flask and was diluted upto the mark with diluent.

Preparation of Sample Solution :

Accurately weighed 10 mg of Palonosetron and Doxorubicin sample into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask and about 7mL of Diluents is added and sonicated to dissolve it completely and made volume upto the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution) Further 3 ml of above stock solution was pipetted into a 10ml volumetric flask and diluted upto the mark with diluent.

Procedure:

20 μ L of the sample are injected into the chromatographic system and the areas for Palonosetron and Doxorubicin peaks are measured and the % Assay are calculated by using the formulae.

Linearity**Preparation of stock solution:**

Accurately 10 tablets were weighed & crushed in mortar and pestle and weight equivalent to 10 mg of Palonosetron and Doxorubicin sample were transferred into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask and about 7mL of Diluent was added and sonicated to dissolve it completely and made volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Preparation of Level – I (20ppm of Doxorubicin&10ppm of Palonosetron):

1ml of stock solution has taken in 10ml of volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluant.

Preparation of Level – II (40ppm of Doxorubicin&20ppm of Palonosetron):

2ml of stock solution has taken in 10ml of volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluant.

Preparation of Level – III (60ppm of Doxorubicin&30ppm of Palonosetron):

3ml of stock solution has taken in 10ml of volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluant.

Preparation of Level – IV (80ppm of Doxorubicin&40ppm of Palonosetron):

4ml of stock solution has taken in 10ml of volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent.

Preparation of Level – V (100ppm of Doxorubicin&50ppm of Palonosetron)

5ml of stock solution has taken in 10ml of volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with diluent.

Procedure:

Each level was injected into the chromatographic system and the peak area was measured. A graph of peak area versus concentration (on X-axis concentration and on Y-axis Peak area) was plotted and the correlation coefficient was calculated.

Acceptance criteria

- Correlation coefficient should be not less than 0.999.

Drug – Excipient Compatibility Study^{14,15}:

Infrared spectroscopy is a useful analytical technique utilized to check the chemical interactions between the drug & excipients used in the formulation. 100-200 mg of solid fine powder of drug and 200-300 mg of dry powder of KBr (IR grade) were taken in a mortar & mixed well with help of a spatula. Spectrum measurement was conducted using KBr disk method in the wavelength region of 4000-400cm⁻¹ by FTIR spectrophotometer. The IR spectrum of the physical mixture have being compared with that of the pure drug to check any possible drug-excipient interaction.

Organoleptic Properties

- Colour:** A small quantity of powders were taken in butter paper and observed in well-illuminated place.
- Taste and odour:** Very less quantity of powders is tasted and perceived to observe the odour as well.

Bulk density determination:^{1,2}

Weighed quantity of the powder (W) is taken in a graduated measuring cylinder and volume (V₀) is measured and bulk density is calculated using the formula.

$$\text{Bulk density (BD)} = \text{Weight of the powder} / \text{Volume of powder}$$

Tapped density determination:^{1,2}

Weighed quantity of powder is taken in a graduated cylinder and the volume is measured (V₀). The graduated cylinder was fixed in the 'Tapped Densimeter' and tapped for 500, 750 and 1250 times until the difference in the volume after consecutive tappings was less than 2%. The final reading was denoted by (V_f). The volume of blend was used to calculate the tapped density, Hausner's ratio and Carr's Index.

$$\text{Tapped density (TD)} = W/V_f \text{ g/ml}$$

Angle of repose:^{3,4}

Angle of Repose is defined as the maximum angle possible between the surface of a pile of the powder and the horizontal plane. The angle of repose is determined by funnel method. The funnel is fixed at a particular height (2.5 cm) on a burette stand. The powder sample was passed through the funnel allowing it to form a pile. No more granule are added as the pile touches the tip of the funnel. This region is encircled to measure radius. The same procedure is done for triplicate, the average value is taken. The angle of repose is calculated by using equation.

$$\text{Angle of Repose } (\theta) = \tan^{-1} (h/r),$$

Where, h = height of pile

r = radius of the base of the pile

θ = angle of repose

Carr's index:^{3,4}

Carr's index is also known as compressibility. It is indirectly related to the relative flow rate, cohesiveness and particle size. It is simple, fast and popular method of predicting powder flow characteristics.

Carr's index was calculated by using the formula:

$$\text{Carr's Index} = \frac{(\text{Tapped Density} - \text{Bulk Density}) \times 100}{\text{Tapped Density}}$$

Hausner ratio:^{3,4}

Hausner ratio indicates the flow properties of the powder and measured by the ratio of tapped density to bulk density. The relationship between Hausner's ratio and flow property Hausner ratio was calculated by using the formula.

$$\text{Hausner Ratio} = \text{Tapped density} / \text{Bulk density}$$

Where V_0 = Initial volume

V_f = Final volume

FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT**Formulation of Bilayer Matrix Tablet (Sustained Release Layer)**

The sustained release tablets containing 50mg doxorubicin were prepared with a total tablet weight of 300mg.

Manufacturing Procedure:

- Micro crystalline cellulose, Hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose were weighed and sifted through 120 mesh.
- To the above blend doxorubicin was added and sifted through 120 mesh.
- The sifted materials have been mixed for 10min.
- PVP K-30 was dissolved in IPA & this solution was added gradually to the above mixture to form a damp mass.
- The wet mass passed through 12 mesh and dried at room temperature.
- The dried granules have been passed through 18 mesh.
- Magnesium Stearate was weighed & sifted through 40 mesh.
- To the dried granules lubricated blend was added and mixed properly.
- The lubricated blend has being compressed using 9mm round punches.

COMPOSITION OF SUSTAINED RELEASE LAYER

Table 1: formulation table for the sustained release layer.

Formulation	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	F ₄	F ₅
Doxorubicin	50mg	50mg	50mg	50mg	50mg
HPMC	30mg	45mg			45mg
Xanthum gum			30mg	45mg	45mg
MCC	199mg	184mg	199mg	184mg	139mg
Mg. stearate	6mg	6mg	6mg	6mg	6mg
PVP K30	15mg	15mg	15mg	15mg	15mg
IPA	qs	qs	qs	qs	qs
Total weight	300mg	300mg	300mg	300mg	300mg

MCC- Micro crystalline cellulose, IPA – Iso propyl alcohol, PVP- Poly vinyl pyrrolidone. All the ingredients are in 'mg'

Formulation of bilayer matrix tablet (immediate layer)

The immediate release tablets comprising 10mg Palonosetron were prepared with a total tablet weight of 150mg.

Manufacturing Procedure:

- Micro crystalline cellulose, super disintegrants like cross povidone, cross carmellose sodium, were weighed and sifted through 160 mesh.
- To the above blend Palonosetron was added and sifted through 160 mesh.
- The sifted materials were mixed for 10min.
- PVP K-30 was dissolved in IPA & this solution was added slowly to the above mixture to form a damp mass.
- The wet mass passed through 12 mesh and dried at room temperature.
- The dried granules have been passed through 18 mesh.
- Magnesium Stearate & talc were weighed and sifted through 40 mesh.
- To the dried granules lubricated blend was added and mixed properly.
- The lubricated blend has being compressed using 9mm-round punches.

COMPOSITION OF IMMEDIATE RELEASE LAYER**Table 2: formulation table for an immediate release layer.**

Formulation	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	F ₄	F ₅	F ₆
Palonosetron	0.5mg	0.5mg	0.5mg	0.5mg	0.5mg	0.5mg
CP	7.5mg	11.25mg	-	-	-	-
CCS	-	-	7.5mg	11.25mg	-	-
SSG	-	-	-	-	7.5mg	11.25 mg
MCC	117.5mg	114.75mg	117.5mg	114.75mg	117.5mg	114.75mg
Magnesium stearate	3 mg					
Talc	1.5mg	1.5mg	1.5mg	1.5mg	1.5mg	1.5mg
Total weight	150	150	150	150	150	150

MCC- microcrystalline cellulose, CP- Crospovidone, CCS: Cross carmellose sodium, SSG: Sodium starch glycolate. All the ingredients are in 'mg'

BILAYERED TABLET COMPRESSION.

After the finishing preparation of granules of both formulations first the doxorubicin granules are filled into the die and compressed later the palonosetron granules were filled and compressed to produce the bilayered tablet.

Figure 1: compression procedure for a bilayered tablet.**EVALUATION OF TABLETS:**

The evaluation of tablets includes, the nature of the active ingredient (identification), expected amount (assay), purity (related compounds), and uniformity of the amount of drug from tablet to tablet (uniformity of dosage units). In addition to these tests, some other tests such as friability, hardness, disintegration, etc. are also conducted.

Assay for Palonosetron and Doxorubicin

Accurately 10 tablets were weighed & crushed in mortar and pestle and weight equivalent to 10 mg of Palonosetron and Doxorubicin sample were transferred into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask and about 7mL of Diluent was added and sonicated to dissolve it completely and made volume up to the mark with the same solvent. The assay study performed for the Palonosetron and Doxorubicin. Each three injections of sample and standard was inject into chromatographic system.

Weight variation test

With a tablet designed to contain a specific amount of drug required, the weight of the tablet being made is routinely measured to help ensure that a tablet contain proper amount of drug. Twenty tablets selected at random and the average weight determined. Not more than two of the individual weights shall deviate from the average weight by more than limit prescribed

Friability:

This test is intended to determine, under defined conditions, the friability of uncoated tablets, the phenomenon whereby tablet surfaces are damaged and/or show evidence of lamination or breakage when subjected to mechanical shock or attrition

Hardness testing:

A tablet requires a certain amount of mechanical strength to withstand the shocks of handling in its manufacturing, packing, shipping and dispensing. As discussed before, hardness and friability are most common measures used to evaluate tablet strength.

Disintegration test:

A disintegration test is a test to establish how fast a tablet disintegrates into aggregates and/or finer particle, the test is conducted using a specially designed instrument known as disintegration apparatus..

In -vitro dissolution studies:

In-vitro release studies were carried out using a modified USP XXIII dissolution test apparatus (Lab India, DS-800). The dissolution fluid was 900ml of pH 1.2 and 6.8 buffers at a speed of 50rpm at a temperature of 37^oc were used in each test. Samples of dissolution medium (5ml) were withdrawn for every 1hr and analyzed using waters HPLC-2690/5 AT 266 nm. For all the tests 5ml of the test medium collected at specified time intervals and replaced with same volume of phosphate buffer PH 6.8.

Details:

Apparatus used	:	USP II Lab India DS 800
Dissolution Medium	:	pH 1.2 Hcl buffer and Phosphate buffer PH 6.8
Dissolution Medium volume	:	900ml
Temperature	:	37 ^o C
Speed of paddle	:	50rpm
Sampling Intervals(SR)	:	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12 hrs
Sampling Intervals(IR)	:	5, 10, 15, 30, 45, 60min.
Sample withdrawn	:	5ml
Absorbance measured	:	266 nm
Beers Range	:	2-100µg/ml

Application of Release Rate Kinetics to Dissolution Data:^{20,21}

Various models were tested for explaining the kinetics of drug release. To analyze the mechanism of the drug release rate kinetics of the dosage form, the obtained data were fitted into zero-order, first order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer-Peppas release model.

Zero order release rate kinetics:

To study the zero-order release kinetics the release rate data are fitted to the following equation.

$$F = K_0 t$$

Where, 'F' is the drug release at time 't', and 'K₀' is the zero order release rate constant. The plot of % drug release versus time is linear.

First order release rate kinetics: The release rate data are fitted to the following equation

$$\text{Log (100-F)} = kt$$

A plot of log cumulative percent of drug remaining to be released vs. time is plotted then it gives first order release.

Higuchi release model: To study the Higuchi release kinetics, the release rate data were fitted to the following equation.

$$F = k t^{1/2}$$

Where, 'k' is the Higuchi constant.

In Higuchi model, a plot of % drug release versus square root of time is linear.

Korsmeyer and Peppas release model:

The mechanism of drug release was evaluated by plotting the log percentage of drug released versus log time according to Korsmeyer- Peppas equation. The exponent 'n' indicates the mechanism of drug release calculated through the slope of the straight Line.

$$M_t / M_\infty = K t^n$$

Where, M_t / M_∞ is fraction of drug released at time 't', k represents a constant, and 'n' is the diffusional exponent, which characterizes the type of release mechanism during the dissolution process. For non-Fickian release, the value of n falls between 0.5 and 1.0; while in case of Fickian diffusion, $n = 0.5$; for zero-order release (case I transport), $n=1$; and for supercase II transport, $n > 1$. In this model, a plot of $\log (M_t / M_\infty)$ versus $\log (\text{time})$ is linear.

Hixson-Crowell release model:

$$(100-Q_t)^{1/3} = 100^{1/3} - K_{HC}.t$$

Where, k is the Hixson-Crowell rate constant.

Hixson-Crowell model describes the release of drugs from an insoluble matrix through mainly erosion.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**Selection of Detection wavelength:**

10 mg of doxorubicin and palonsetron was dissolved in mobile phase. The solution was scanned from 200-400 nm the spectrum was obtained. The overlay spectrum was used for selection of wavelength for doxorubicin and palonsetron. The isobestic point was taken as detection wavelength.

The detection wavelength was selected by dissolving the drug in mobile phase to get a concentration of 10 μ g/ml for individual and mixed standards. The resulting solution was scanned in U.V range from 200-400nm. The overlay spectrum of doxorubicin and palonsetron was obtained and the isobestic point of doxorubicin and palonsetron showed absorbance's maxima at 266 nm.

Figure 2: Overlay spectrum of doxorubicin and palonsetron.

Optimized conditions for the method development.**Chromatographic conditions:**

Column : Inertsil C18 5 μ m (4.6*250mm)
 Mobile phase ratio : Phosphate buffer (0.05M)
 pH 4.6 : ACN (30:70%v/v)
 Detection wavelength : 266nm
 Flow rate : 1ml/min
 Injection volume : 20 μ l
 Column temperature : Ambient

Figure 3: chromatogram of doxorubicin and palonosetron.

Linearity Results

Table 3: Linearity results of Doxorubicin and Palonosetron.

S. no	Sample name	Name	RT	Area	Height (μV)
1	Linearity 1	Doxorubicin	2.309	1810101	145957
2	Linearity 1	Palonosetron	4.307	1164173	75128
3	Linearity 2	Doxorubicin	2.322	2065287	176935
4	Linearity 2	Palonosetron	4.317	1342535	87703
5	Linearity 3	Doxorubicin	2.324	2337133	206622
6	Linearity 3	Palonosetron	4.323	1555931	101999
7	Linearity 4	Doxorubicin	2.336	2602279	228576
8	Linearity 4	Palonosetron	4.340	1747973	117084
9	Linearity 5	Doxorubicin	2.345	2869778	259346
10	Linearity 5	Palonosetron	4.340	1942319	129409

Acceptance Criteria:

Correlation coefficient should be not less than 0.999

Plotting of calibration graphs:

The resultant areas of linearity peaks are plotted against Concentration.

Figure 4: Calibration curve of Doxorubicin.

Figure 5: Calibration curve of Palonosetron.

Compatibility studies:

Figure 6: FTIR Spectra of Palonosetron.

Figure 7: FTIR Spectra of doxorubicin.

Figure 8: FTIR Spectra of drugs with polymers.

Observation

Compatibility studies were performed using FTIR spectrophotometer. The FTIR spectrum of pure drug and physical mixtures of drug, polymers and excipients were studied. The peaks obtained in the spectra of physical mixtures of drug, polymers and excipients were correlated with the peaks of drug spectrum. From the FTIR spectrum, it was concluded that no significant shift in peak pattern in IR spectrum of drug and physical mixtures of drug, polymers and excipients.

Assay of doxorubicin and palonosetron

Figure 9: assay chromatogram of doxorubicin and palonosetron.

Observation:

The system suitability parameters for doxorubicin and palonosetron such as theoretical plates and tailing factor were found to be 5117.5, 1.3 and 3877.3, 1.4. Resolution was 8.1. The % purity of doxorubicin and palonosetron in pharmaceutical dosage form was found to be 100.7% and 101.4% respectively.

Table 4: evaluation of pre-compression parameters for sustained release layer of doxorubicin.

Formulations	Angle of Repose (θ)	Loose Bulk Density (g/cc)	Tapped Bulk Density (g/cc)	%Compressibility	Hausner's ratio
F1	32.6 \pm 0.59	0.423 \pm 0.006	0.62 \pm 0.06	16.8 \pm 1.23	1.17 \pm 0.02
F2	35.9 \pm 0.35	0.421 \pm 0.012	0.65 \pm 0.05	16.4 \pm 1.34	1.14 \pm 0.01
F3	31.2 \pm 0.48	0.427 \pm 0.054	0.577 \pm 0.03	16.7 \pm 1.24	1.15 \pm 0.05
F4	32.5 \pm 0.49	0.453 \pm 0.024	0.655 \pm 0.07	19.4 \pm 1.11	1.14 \pm 0.04
F5	31.6 \pm 0.78	0.430 \pm 0.042	0.663 \pm 0.01	15.6 \pm 1.25	1.14 \pm 0.08

n=3, \pm S.D

From the above pre-compression parameters it was clear evidence that drug and excipients has poor flow properties so granulation method is preferable.

Table 5: Post compression parameters to sustained release tablets.

Formulations	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Thickness (mm)	Friability (%)
F1	3.3 ±0.54	3.18±0.17	0.46
F2	3.6±0.11	3.55±0.22	0.49
F3	3.1±0.50	3.02±0.80	0.42
F4	3.3±0.75	3.62±0.20	0.32
F5	3.0±0.55	3.44±0.21	0.31

n=3, ±S.D

INVITRO DISSOLUTION STUDIES FOR SR TABLETS -DISSOLUTION STUDY (SR TABLETS) :**Acidic Stage:**

Medium : 0.1N HCL

Time : 2hrs

Buffer Stage:

Medium : 6.8pH phosphate buffer

Type of apparatus : USP - II (paddle type)

RPM : 50

Volume : 900ml

Time : 10hrs

In vitro dissolution for SR tablets were done in 6.8 phosphate buffer for 12hrs

In-Vitro Drug Release Studies for SR tablets

After the dissolution testing the samples were analyzed using HPLC and calculated for % drug release in the selected time period

Table 6: cumulative percentage drug release of sustained layer.

Time(hrs)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
1	42±1.25	52.8±1.21	38±1.56	48.2±1.24	33±0.51
2	68±0.34	78.2±1.15	51±1.41	69.3±1.33	48±0.67
3	86±1.24	100.2±1.37	68±0.36	80.5±1.52	52±0.86
4	98.9±1.52	-	89.2±0.41	92.8±1.62	61.5±0.78
6	-	-	94.8±1.01	99.8±1.31	69±0.61
8	-	-	100.5±1.59	-	73±0.94
10	-	-	-	-	80±0.81
12	-	-	-	-	86.6±0.88

n=3, ±S.D

Figure 10: Dissolution graph for the sustained release formulations.

KINETIC RELEASE MODELS:**Table 7 release kinetics for F5 formulations for the sustained release layer.**

RELEASE KINETICS				
	ZERO	HIGUCHI	PEPPAS	FIRST
	Q Vs T	Q Vs \sqrt{T}	Log C Vs Log T	Log % Remain Vs T
Slope	5.73	23.82	1.03	-0.06
R 2	0.795	0.967	0.479	0.962

Discussion for in-vitro release of doxorubicin layer SR

From the table, it was confirmed that the F1, F2, F3, F4 of SR layer doesn't fulfill the sustained release theory. And also from the table, it was also confirmed such formulation done with HPMC (15%) and Xanthum gum (15%) showed sustained release up to 12hrs.

Evaluation parameters for the immediate release layer of palonosetron**Pre compression parameters****Table 8: precompression parameters of Palonosetron.**

Formulations	Angle of Repose (θ)	Loose Bulk Density (g/cc)	Tapped Bulk Density (g/cc)	%Compressibility	Hausner's ratio
F1	31.6 \pm 1.02	0.463 \pm 0.056	0.663 \pm 0.042	15.60 \pm 1.24	1.14 \pm 0.02
F2	35.8 \pm 1.08	0.412 \pm 0.047	0.646 \pm 0.052	17.75 \pm 1.34	1.16 \pm 0.03
F3	33.4 \pm 0.34	0.435 \pm 0.024	0.634 \pm 0.063	17.40 \pm 1.27	1.15 \pm 0.08
F4	34.2 \pm 0.48	0.452 \pm 0.024	0.648 \pm 0.048	17.70 \pm 1.23	1.10 \pm 0.09
F5	32.5 \pm 0.75	0.453 \pm 0.27	0.655 \pm 0.041	19.40 \pm 1.32	1.14 \pm 0.04
F6	35.6 \pm 0.47	0.422 \pm 0.036	0.647 \pm 0.052	17.20 \pm 1.42	1.13 \pm 0.09

n=3, \pm S.D

From the above pre-compression parameters it was clear evidence that drug and excipients has poor flow properties so granulation method is preferable.

Post compression evaluations parameters to immediate release formulation.

The results of the uniformity of weight, hardness, thickness, friability, and drug content of the tablets are given in Table . All the tablets of various batches complied with official requirements of uniformity of weight as their weights varied between 147 \pm 0.53 to 151 \pm 0.06. The hardness of the tablets ranged from 4.0 \pm 0.44 to 5.5 \pm 0.37 kg/cm² and the friability values has been >0.5% suggesting that the matrix tablets were compact and hard. The thickness of the tablets ranged from to 2.27 \pm 0.23 to 2.68 \pm 0.27 mm. Thus, all the physical attributes of the prepared tablets to be practically within control.

Table 9: Post compression parameters for immediate release tablets.

Physical parameters	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
Weight variation	147 \pm 0.53	148 \pm 0.27	148 \pm 0.56	149 \pm 0.52	149 \pm 0.17	151 \pm 0.06
Hardness (Kg/cm ²)	2.5 \pm 0.37	2.5 \pm 0.54	2.3 \pm 0.11	2.5 \pm 0.98	2.0 \pm 0.44	2.3 \pm 0.21
Thickness (mm)	2.68 \pm 0.27	2.64 \pm 0.83	2.65 \pm 0.32	2.27 \pm 0.23	2.52 \pm 0.20	2.52 \pm 0.54
Friability %	0.37	0.41	0.42	0.38	0.39	0.41
Disintegration time	8min	5min	7min 20sec	3min	5min 40sec	2min 30sec

n=3, \pm S.D**Drug release studies:**

After the dissolution testing the samples were analyzed using HPLC and calculated for % drug release in the selected time period

Table 10: Dissolution for an immediate release tablet of Palonosetron.

Time	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
5	3.76 \pm 0.15	3.53 \pm 0.45	9 \pm 0.82	12 \pm 1.05	12 \pm 0.21	10 \pm 1.24
10	11.7 \pm 0.84	8.24 \pm 0.82	18 \pm 0.57	28 \pm 1.06	24 \pm 0.29	21 \pm 1.42
15	8.01 \pm 1.24	13.6 \pm 0.91	33 \pm 1.21	36 \pm 1.48	38 \pm 0.67	42 \pm 1.63
30	15.5 \pm 1.68	33.92 \pm 1.24	41 \pm 1.62	52 \pm 1.86	43 \pm 1.64	54 \pm 1.48
45	20.2 \pm 1.75	49.71 \pm 1.37	53 \pm 1.46	69 \pm 1.89	58 \pm 1.27	68 \pm 1.51
60	25 \pm 1.64	60.4 \pm 1.86	62 \pm 1.83	80 \pm 1.91	67 \pm 1.33	98 \pm 1.34

n=3, \pm S.D

Figure 11: Dissolution graph for formulations F1-F6.

From the drug release data it was confirmed that palonosetron formulation F6 gave desired drug release in the selected period of time

CONCLUSION

The Bilayered tablets containing Doxorubicin SR and palonosetron IR successfully prepared by wet granulation method respectively. The physicochemical evaluation results found to be within limits. Bottom line is we have successfully prepared and evaluated doxorubicin-SR and palonosetron-IR bilayer tablets. The success of the work is based on the analytical method (HPLC), compatibility studies (FTIR), and dissolution profiles. The prepared combination gives pleasant experience during the chemotherapeutic treatment by relieving the patient from nausea effects. This might be proved in future by conducting invivo studies as well as studies on humans

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Conflicts of interest:

The authors express no conflicts of interest regarding the publication, all the authors worked and provided support equally and credited equally.

Abbreviations:

%	-PERCENTAGE
CAN	-ACETONITRILE
CCS	-CROSSCARMELLOSE SODIUM
CM-	CENTIMETER
CP	-CROSSPOVIDONE
DAN	-DALTONS
F1-F6	-FORMULATION
FTIR	-FOURIER TRANSFORM INFRARED SPECTROSCOPY
GM	-GRAM
HPLC	-HIGH PERFORMANCE LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY
HPMC	-HYDROXY PROPYL METHYL CELLULOSE
HPMC	-HYDROXY PROPYL METHYLCELLULOSE
IPA	-ISO PROPYL ALCOHOL
IR	- IMMEDIATE RELEASE
KG	-KILOGRAM
KH ₂ PO ₄	- POTASSIUM DI HYDROGEN ORTHO PHOSPHATE
MCC	-MICRO CRYSTALLINE CELLULOSE
MG	-MILLIGRAM
MM	-MILLIMETER
N	-NUMNER OF TIMES
PVP K30	-POLY VINYL PYRROLIDONE
S.D	- STANDARD DEVIATION
SR	-SUSTAINED RELEASE
SSG	-SODIUM STARCH GLYCOLLATE
UV	-ULTRAVIOLET
MI	-MICRO LITER

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